

VERMICOMPOSTING : PROFITABLE ORGANIC FERTILIZER**Sunita Arya**

Associate Professor Deptt of Zoology, D.G. College, Kanpur

E-mail : greenindia2@gmail.com

Abstract

The production of degradable organic waste animal and its disposal becomes the current problem. Mean while the rejuvenation of degraded soils by protecting top soil and sustainability of productive soil is a major concern at the international level. Provision of a sustainable environment in the soil by amending with good quality organic soil additive enhances the water holding capacity and nutrient supply capacity of soil and also the development of resistance in plants to pests and diseases. By reducing the time of unification process and by evolving the methods to minimize the loss of nutrients during the course of decomposition, the fantasy becomes fact. Earthworms can serve as tools to facilitate these functions. The serve as Nature's Plowman" and form nature's fit to produce good human, which is to most precious material to fullfill the nutritional needs of crops.

Introduction :

Vermicompost is the product of the composing process using various species of worms, usually red wigglers, white worms and other earthworms, to create mixture of decomposing.

Organic material like plant and animal wastes. One can get excellent profits by commercial production of vermicomposts as the use of this increasing day by day. The earthworms promote faster decomposition of organic material when compared to compost pits without earthworms. After using vermicompost in most of the crops, it has been found that germination percentage as well as produce quality is very high. A part from supplying nutrients and growth enhancing hormones to plant,

improves the soil structure leading increase in water and nutrient holding capacities of soil (Nagavallemana *et al.*, 2004).

In short we can say earthworms are capable to convert garbage in to gold (Tura, 2003; Vermi, 2001).

Organic nutrients increase the abundance of soil organisms by providing organic matter and micronutrients for organisms such as fungal mycorrhiza, (which aid plants in absorbing nutrients), and can drastically reduce external inputs of pesticides, energy and fertilizer, at the cost of decreased yield.

Vermi-composting

Vermi-composting is a simple biotechnological process of composting, in which certain species of earthworms are used to increase the process of waste conversion and produce a profitable end produce. It prepared with the use of microorganisms and earthworms that are active at 10-32°C (not ambient temperature but temperature within the pile of moist organic material). The process is faster than composting; because the material passes through the earthworm gut, a significant but not yet fully understood transformation takes place, whereby the resulting earthworm castings (worm manure) are rich in microbial activity and plant growth regulators, and fortified with pest repellence attributes as well.

IMPORTANCE OF VERMICOMPOST

Source of plant nutrients

Earthworms take various organic wastes and reduce the volume by 40-60%. Each earthworm weighs about 0.5 to 0.6 g, eats waste equivalent to its body weight and produces cast equivalent to about 50% of the waste it consumes in a day. These worm castings have been analyzed for chemical and biological properties. The moisture content of castings ranges between 32 and 66% and the pH is around 7.0. The worm castings contain higher percentage (nearly twofold) of both macro and micronutrients than the garden compost. From earlier studies also it is

evident that vermicompost provides all nutrients in readily available form and also enhances uptake of nutrients by plants. Sreenivas *et al.* (2000) studied the integrated effect of application of fertilizer and vermicompost on soil available nitrogen (N) and uptake of ridge gourd (*Luffa acutangula*) at Rajendranagar, Andhra Pradesh, India. Soil available N increased significantly with increasing levels of vermicompost and highest N uptake was obtained at 50% of the recommended fertilizer rate plus 10 t ha⁻¹ vericompost (Jadhav *et al.*, 2015).

Improved crop growth and yield

Vermicompost plays a major role in improving growth and yield of different field crops, vegetables, flower and fruit crops. The application of vermicompost gave higher germination (93%) of mung bean (*Vigna radiata*) compared to the control (84%). Further, the growth and yield of mung bean was also significantly higher with vermicompost application. Likewise, in another pot experiment, the fresh and dry matter yields of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) were higher when soil was amended with vermicompost than with bio-digested slurry (Karmegam and Daniel, 2000, Karmegam *et al.*, 2015).

Desai *et al.*, 1999, Studies the efficiency of vermicompost in a field. The reported that the application of vermicompost along with fertilizer N gave higher dry matter (16.4 plant⁻¹) and grain yield (4.6 t ha⁻¹) of wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) and higher dry matter yield (0.69 g plant⁻¹) of the following coriander (*Coriandrum sativum*) crop in sequential cropping system. Similarly, a positive response was found with the application of vermicompost to other field crops such as sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) (Patil and Sheelavantar 2000) and sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) (Devi and Agarwal, 1988). Application of vermicompost at 5 t ha⁻¹ significantly increased yield of tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) (5.8 t ha⁻¹) in farmers' fields in Adarsha watershed, Kothapally, Andhra Pradesh compared to control (3.5 t ha⁻¹). Similarly, greenhouse studies at Ohio

State University in Columbus, Ohio, USA have indicated that vermicompost improve transplant growth rate of vegetables. The production of pea (*Pisum sativum*) was found also higher with the application of vermicompost (10 t ha⁻¹) along with recommended N, P and K than with these manure alone (Reddy *et al.* 1998). Vadiraj *et al.* (1998) reported that application of vermicompost produced herbage yields of coriander cultivars that were comparable to those obtained with chemical fertilizers (ICRISAT and APRLP 2003).

The fresh weight of flowers such as *Chrysanthemum chinensis* increased with the application of different levels of vermicompost. Also, the number of flowers per plant (26), flower diameter (6 cm) and yield (0.5 t ha⁻¹) were maximum with the application of 10 t ha⁻¹ of vermicompost along with 50% of recommended dose of NPK fertilizer. However, the vase life of flowers (ii days) was high with the combined application of vermicompost at 15 t ha⁻¹ (Hussaini, 2013).

Reduction in soil C: N ratio

Vermicomposting transformed household waste into compost within 30-35 days, reduces the C: N ratio and retains more N than the traditional methods of preparing composts (Munroe, 2007). The C: N ratio of the unprocessed olive cake, vermicomposted olive cake and manure were 42, 29 and 11, respectively. Both the unprocessed olive cake and vermicomposted olive cake immobilized soil N throughout the study duration of 91 days. Cattle manure mineralized an appreciable amount of N during the study. The results suggest that for use of vermicomposted dry olive cake as an organic soil amendment, the management of vermicomposting process should be so adjusted as to ensure more favorable N mineralization immobilization, Sinha (2008).

Improved soil physical, chemical and biological properties

Limited studies on vermicompost indicate that it increases macro pore space ranging from 50 to 500 µm, resulting in improved air-water

relationship in the soil which favorably affects plant growth (George, 2004). The application of organic matter including vermicompost favorably affects soil PH, microbial population and soil enzyme activities. It also reduces the proportion of water-soluble chemical species, which cause possible environmental contamination, Bhadauria and Ramakrishnan (1996).

Methods of Vermicomposting

1. Pits below the ground Pits

Are made for vermicomposting are 1 m deep and 1.5 m wide. The length varies as required.

2. Heaping above the ground

The waste material is spread on a polythene sheet placed on the ground and then covered with cattle dung. Bogdanov (1996) compared the efficacy of pit and heap methods of preparing vermicompost under field conditions. Considering the biodegradation of wastes as the criterion, the heap method of preparing vermicompost was better than the pit method. Earthworm population was high in the heap method, with a 21-fold increase in *Euq'rilus eugeniae* as compared to 17-fold increase in the pit method. Biomass production was also higher in the heap method (46-fold increase) than in the pit method (31-fold). Consequent production of vermicompost was higher in the heap method (51 kg) than in the pit method (40 kg).

3. Tanks above the ground

Tanks made up of different materials such as normal bricks, hollow bricks, shabaz stones, asbestos sheets and locally available rocks were evaluated for vermicompost preparation. Tanks can be constructed with the dimensions suitable for operations. At ICRISAT, we have evaluated tanks with dimensions of 1.5 m (5 feet) Width, 4.5 m (15 feet) length and 0.9 m (3 feet) height. The commercial biodigester contains a partition wall

with small holes to facilitate easy movement of earthworms from one tank to the other.

4. Cement rings

Vermicompost can also be prepared above the ground by using cement rings (ICRISAT and APRLP 2003). The size of the cement ring should be 90 cm in diameter and 30 cm in height. The details of preparing vermicompost by this method have been described in a later section.

5. Commercial model

The commercial model for vermicomposting developed by ICRISAT consists of four chambers enclosed by a wall (1.5 m width, 4.5 m length and 0.9 m height) (Fig. 1.1). The walls are made up of different materials such as normal bricks, hollow bricks, shabaz stones, asbestos sheets and locally available rocks. This model contains partition walls with small holes to facilitate easy movement of earthworms from one chamber to another. Providing an outlet at one corner of each chamber with a slight slope facilitates collection of excess water, which is reused later or used as earthworm leach, ate on crop. The outline of the commercial model is given in Figure 1.1. The four components of a tank are filled with plant residues one after another. The first chamber is filled layer by layer along with cow dung and then earthworms are released. Then the second chamber is filled layer by layer. Once the contents in the first chamber are processed the earthworms move to chamber 2, which is already filled and ready for earthworms. This facilitates harvesting of decomposed material from the first chamber and also saves labor for harvesting and introducing earthworms. This technology reduces labor cost, saves water and time.

Vermicompost Preparation Steps in the process

Vermicomposting involves the following steps:

- Cover the bottom of the cement ring with a layer of tiles or coconut husk or polythene sheet.

- Spread 15-20 cm layer of organic waste material on the polythene sheet. Sprinkle rock phosphate powder if available (it helps in improving nutritional quality of compost) on the waste material and then sprinkle cow dung slurry.
- Fill the ring completely in layers as described. Paste the top of the ring with soil or cow dung. Allow the material to decompose for 15 to 20 days.
- When the heat evolved during the decomposition of the materials has subsided (15-20 days after heaping), release selected earthworms (500 to 700) through the cracks developed.
- Cover the ring with wire mesh or gunny bag to prevent birds from picking the earthworms. Sprinkle water every three days to maintain adequate moisture and body temperature.
- The vermicompost is ready in about 2 months if agricultural waste is used and about 4 weeks if sericulture waste is used as substrate.

The processed vermicompost is black, light in weight and free from bad odor. When the compost is ready, do not water for 2-3 days to make compost easy for sifting. Pile the compost in small heaps and leave under ambient conditions for a couple of hours when all the worms move down the heap in the bed. Separate upper portion of the manure and sieve the lower portion to separate the earthworms from the manure. The culture in the bed contains different stages of the earthworm's life cycle, namely, cocoons, juveniles and adults. Transfer this culture to fresh half decomposed feed material. The excess as well as big earthworms can be used for feeding fish or poultry. Pack the compost in bags and store the bags in a cool place. Prepare another pile about 20 days before removing the compost and repeat the process by following the same procedure as described above.

1. Precautions during the process

The following precautions should be taken during vermicomposting :

The African species of earthworms, *Eisenia fetida* and *Eudrilus eugeniae* are ideal for the preparation of vermicompost. Most Indian species are not suitable for the purpose. Only plant-based materials such as grass, leaves or vegetable peelings should be utilized in preparing vermicompost. Materials of animal origin such as eggshells, meat, bone, chicken droppings, etc are not suitable for preparing vermicompost. *Gliricidia* lopping and tobacco leaves are not suitable for rearing earthworms. The earthworms should be protected against birds, termites, ants and rats. Adequate moisture should be maintained during the process. Either stagnant water or lack of moisture could kill the earthworms. After completion of the process, the vermicompost should be removed from the bed at regular intervals and replaced by fresh waste materials.

How to Use Vermicompost?

1. Vermicompost can be used for all crops: agricultural, horticultural, ornamental and vegetables at any stage of the crop.
2. **For general field crops:** Around 2-3 t ha⁻¹ vermicompost is used by mixing with seed at the time of sowing or by row application when the seedlings are 12-15 cm in height. Normal irrigation is followed.
3. **For fruit trees:** The amount of vermicompost ranges from 5 to 10 kg per tree depending on the age of the plant. For efficient application, a ring (15-18 cm deep) is made around the plant. A thin layer of dry cow dung and bone meal is spread along with 2-5 kg of vermicompost and water is sprayed on the surface after covering with soil.
4. **For vegetables:** For raising seedlings to be transplanted, vermicompost at 1 t ha⁻¹ is applied in the nursery bed. This results in healthy and vigorous seedlings. But for transplants, vermicompost at the rate of 400-500 g per plant is applied initially at the time of planting and 45 days after planting (before irrigation).

5. For vegetable and flower crops vermicompost is applied around the base of the plant. It is then covered with soil and watered regularly. For flowers: Vermicompost is applied at 750-1000 kg ha⁻¹.

Reference :

- Bogdanov, P. (1996). Commercial vermiculture : How to build a thriving business in red worms, Vermico Press, *Oregon.*, **83** : 18, 79-92.
- George (2004). Feasibility of developing the organic and transitional farm market for processing municipal and farm organic waste using large scale vermicomposting, Pub. of Good Earth Organic Resources group. Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada.
- Munroe, G. (2007). Manual of on farm vermicomposting and vermiculture, Pub. organic agric centre of Canada, PP : 39.
- Hussaini, A. (2013). Vermiculture Biotechnology : An affective tool for economic and environmental sustainability. *African J. Environ. Sci. Tech.*, **7** (2) : 56-60.
- Sinha, R.K. (2008). Organic farming : An economic solution for food safety and environmental security. *Green Farming International J. Agric. Sci.*, **1** (10-11) : 42-49.
- Dessai, V.R.; Sabale, R.N. and Raundal, P.V. (1999). Integrated Nitrogen management in wheat coriander cropping system. *J. Maharashtra Agric. Univ.*, **24** (3) : 273-275.
- ICRISAT and APRLP (2003). Vermi composting : Conversion of organic waste into valuable manure. Andhra Pradesh, India : ICRISAT and APRLP, PP 4.

- Karmegam, N. and Daniel, T. (2000). Effect of biodigested slurry and vermicompost on the growth and yield of cowpea. *Environment and Ecology*, **18** (2) : 367-370.
- Patil, S.L. and Sheelavantar, M.N. (2000). Effect of moisture conservation practices, organic sources and nitrogen levels on yield, water use and root development of rabi sorghum in the vertisols of semi arid tropics. *Annals of Agricultural Res.*, **21** (2) : 32-36.
- Vermi Co. (2001). Vermicomposting technology for waste management and agriculture : An executive summary, PO Box 2334, Grants Pass Or 97528, USA : Vermi Co.
- Wani, S.P. and Lee, K.K. (1992). Biofertilizers role in upland crops production, PP 91-112 in Fertilizers, organic manure recyclable wastes and biofertilizers, New Delhi, India.
- Zajonc, I and Sidor, V. (1990). Use of some wastes for vermicompost preparation and their influence on growth and reproduction of earthworm. *Pol. Nohpodars-tvo (CSFR)*, **36** (8) : 742-752.
- Sreenivas, C.; Muralidhar, S. and Rao, M.S. (2000). Vermicompost, available, component of IPNSS in nitrogen nutrition of ridge ground. *Ann. Agric. Res.*, **2** (1) : 108-113.
- Tara, Crescent (2003). Vermicomposting Development alternatives sustainable livelihoods. (<http://www.daniet.org/livelihood/default.htm>).
- Jadav, R.; Achutan, C.; Gleb, H.; Shireen, R. and Risto, R. (2015). *J. Agromedicine*, **20** : 434-449.
- Karmegam, N.; Nagraj, R.; Karuppusamy and Prakash, M.M. (2015). Biological and pharmacological activities of *Andrographis* spp. distributed in Southern Gluts, India. *International J. Current. Biosci. and Plant Bio.*, **2** (9) : 140-153.

Nagavallema, K.P.; Wani, S.P.; Stephane, L.; Padmaja, V.V.; Vineela, C.; Rao, M.B. and Sahrawat, K.L. (2004). Vermicomposting recycling wastes into valuable organic fertilizer. Andhra Pradesh Rural Livelihoods Programm. *Bulletin*, PP : 1-23.

Bhadauria, T. and Ramakrishnan, P.S. (1996). Role of earthworms in nitrogen cucle during the cropping phase of shifting agriculture in Northeast India. *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, **22** : 350-354.

